

Environmentally-Mediated Epigenetic Effects: Uncovering the Fertile Soil in the Development of Pediatric Cancer

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Image:

Abstract:

Objectives: We reviewed the literature to identify the evidence about the potential link between the environmental effects & the increased susceptibility to pediatric cancer, and explained how these factors may be transferred to initiate & promote the development of pediatric cancer through epigenetic mechanisms.

Methods: First, we highlighted the role of epigenetics in embryogenesis & development, and then we presented some evidence from animal models about trans-generational inheritance & the potential transfer of environmental effects through multiple generations to effect development of disease phenotypes by evolutionary epigenetic remodeling or even could drive genomic variations at the long term. In addition, we addressed some studies that relate specific environmental exposures to the increased susceptibility to specific pediatric cancer types, and finally we shed the light on aberrant reprogramming in early developmental stages & the potential link between developmental malformations & childhood cancer.

Results: The environmentally-acquired epigenetic marks may influence the control of gene regulation through DNA methylation,

histone modification, or through a large set of non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs). These epigenetic effects might be passed on to the developing embryo and child as inheritable non-genetic marks, which recapitulate previous lifelong history of exposure to environmental influences that start from the stage of primordial germ cell, passing through the maturing germ cell, and ending by the zygote stage. This involves the paternally transmitted information on the sperm that contribute to modulating embryogenesis functions and later childhood development, in concert with, the maternally transmitted information encountered by the exposure to a large milieu of environmental factors either periconceptionally or during lactation period.

Conclusion: Environmentally-mediated epigenetic effects could have a clue for unique criteria that have been associated with pediatric cancer, such as presence of global epigenetic changes, heterogeneity, diversity, and regression of some tumors. To uncover many of unanswered questions, more focused research should be carried out through longitudinal studies that address the effects of various environmental influences involving successive generations using integrated genetic & epigenetic approaches to gain insights & accumulate further evidence about the interplay between genetics, epigenetics & exposure, and its possible role in initiation, promotion & progression of different pediatric tumors.

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Biography:

Ahmed Mohammed Morsy graduated in Medicine from Assiut University in 2001. Following finishing his residency program at the Pediatric Oncology Department - Assiut University; he was appointed an Assistant Lecturer after obtaining a Master's Degree in Pediatrics in 2007. Dr. Morsy is currently a Lecturer after he was awarded the MD Degree in Pediatric Oncology in 2014.

Dr. Morsy also has published some original research and review articles in peer-reviewed journals which have an international reputation. He is a member of the Editorial Board and also works as a Reviewer for many peer-reviewed scientific medical journals. Dr. Ahmed Morsy's research interests include issues related to childhood cancer either the clinical or translational aspects of hematologic malignancies or solid tumors in children with cancer.

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Notes/Comments:

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